

THE BRAND AND BRANDING FOR THE BUCOVINA TOURISM PRODUCT

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ABSTRACT

Bucovina's ancient cradle of culture and civilization is known as an area with a varied tourist potential due to the variety of natural landscapes that are of particular tourist importance. In addition, other natural resources, natural reserves and anthropic tourist attractions are added, such as the northern Bucovina Monasteries, which are included in the UNESCO World Heritage by interior and exterior frescoes, being internally and internationally recognized. Due to the presence of these natural and anthropic tourist attractions, the Bucovina area can become a world-renowned brand. In recent years, with the launch of the country brand, there have been concerns about the establishment of the brand specific to this so-called area, in order to promote tourist settlements on the national and international tourist market. Branding is defined as the process by which brand and identity are created and developed. Bucovina is recognized as an attractive tourist area of Romania, more and more sought after by domestic and foreign tourists, it has a defining element that categorically differentiates it from the other Romanian tourist areas, namely UNESCO heritage monasteries.

Keywords: marketing, brand, branding, tourism, tourist product, Bucovina area

INTRODUCTION

The concept of tourist product appears to be related both to the offer of tourism agencies and to some tourist areas, such as Bucovina, Delta, Transylvania, Oltenia, Muntenia, etc. They have become true "tourist brands of Romania". The regional tourism promotion associations, the tourist information centers and the tourist promotion offices of Romania, together with the decision-makers in the public administration, respectively the National Authority for Tourism, should devise strategies for setting up and promoting the important tourist brands of Romania. As far as the tourist brand is concerned, it represents the image element that identifies the tourist products or services of a tourist area, regions that generate the pride of the inhabitants of this area, recognition and satisfaction among consumers. A brand is made from a logo, a slogan, but its strength results from all the media that it is communicated and promoted: directly through audio-video spots, prints, online banners, posters, catalogs, direct mail.

At the same time, even if hundreds of thousands of dollars are invested in tourism brand communication campaigns, it is up to consumers to decide whether the brand meets the expectations of tourists. Tourism branding is a process of creating and maintaining a brand in the hospitality industry, all the methods by which an organization or product communicates, symbolizes and differentiates itself from its audiences. Tourist branding consists in identifying or creating, exploiting sustainable competitive advantages, in our case being the strengths of the Bucovina product or tourist area.

One can thus speak of a development process of a tourism product, its launch on the national and international tourist market and especially the connection between the consumer and the product on account of the product's qualities ("uniqueness").

The benefits of a successful tourist branding for Bucovina are:

1. Differentiating the Bucovina tourism product from other products in a unique, relevant and motivating way for potential customers.
2. Increasing the perception of the value of the global product by boosting and sustaining the sale price of the particular tourist products related to Bucovina (eg pilgrimage touristic touristic packages, tourist package for active tourism, stays in hotels or tourist hostels in the area).
3. Offer the possibility of launching new products faster and more cost-effectively.

Bucovina is a tourist destination within Romania's tourism macroproducts.

Thus, in the case of foreign tourists who make a 10 day voyage in our country, the Bucovina area is usually allocated 2 days.

In countries with tradition in the hospitality industry, there are 12 day tourist programs where tourists do not have time to get bored. A tourist product that is going on for ten days in Bucovina would not be possible for now, because the foreign tourist is a dynamic amateur of programs you have to offer me.

An attraction such as the monasteries of Bucovina or Dracula Park must be the main reason for the foreign tourists to be attracted to Romania, and once they arrive, they will be oriented towards the other tourist attractions.

The reality in the territory shows that the incoming activity is poorly developed in the Bucovina area as in the other areas of Romania. The vast majority of Romanian travel agencies mainly carry out an outgoing activity, which is now considered by local operators as more profitable.

Taking into account that the demand for domestic tourism is currently decreasing and will follow this trend until the economic situation of the population improves, the marketing efforts should be oriented towards attracting as many tourists as possible to the Bucovina area foreigners from developed countries.

Data provided by statistics show that the number of foreign tourists and overnight stays is low compared to the accommodation possibilities and tourist potential of the area, and from the top five tourists' countries of origin (Russia, Germany, Moldova, Austria, Ukraine) only Germany and Austria could be considered countries whose tourists also have a consistent budget for spending a holiday in Bukovina.

What we want to point out is that not the number of foreign tourists visiting a site matters, but how much they get from them. Thus, we note that tourists from neighboring countries come and come to the Bucovina area for that small border traffic.

In the Bucovina area, tourists come in organized groups, within circuits designed, distributed and promoted by the tour operators in Bucharest. As a result, it is necessary to design marketing strategies that aim at keeping tourists as much as possible in the area.

For this it is necessary to develop a correct marketing strategy at the level of the whole tourist area of Bucovina. In this regard, it is necessary to collaborate with all those involved and interested in the development of the hospitality industry in the region in order to determine the content of the tourist programs that will be promoted under the "Bucovina brand".

Concerning the Bucovina brand, it is worth mentioning an initiative of the three mountain resorts in Suceava County (Vatra Dornei, Campulung-Moldovenesc and Gura Humorului) that will no longer organize similar tourist events during the same period of the year, so that events more overlapping. As a tourist brand for each Suceava mountain resort, Câmpulung Moldovenesc gave up organizing the Snow Celebrations, as this type of event is a recognized and successful brand of Vatra Dornei.

Because the mountainous area of Suceava County has all the year's events to attract tourists, the main resorts in the county are meant to organize festivals every season. Thus, for the winter season, "Winter Holidays" will be organized in Vatra Dornei, a manifestation that takes place for eight weeks with various concerts and competitions of winter sports.

In Campulung Moldovenesc, the Spring Festival will be held every year at the beginning of March and at the end of August-early September, the Autumn Festival, a farmers festival and one of the forest fruits, while in June will be organized in the Gura Humorului resort, the City Festival, with national and international actions such as "Humor at Gura Humorului".

In this way all events will attract tourists to the three mountain resorts of national interest of Suceava County throughout the year. Until now, they were in a fake competition, each wanting to attract tourists during season periods, but it was considered that there are no periods of over-season in Bucovina and in these conditions each resort should be complementary to the other throughout the season year.

The Suceava mountain resorts should create brands related to these festivals, which together form part of the Bucovina brand.

Bucovina is not just monasteries, but also mountain tourism, recreational tourism or wellness tourism.

An upward trend is business tourism, many large firms or professional associations, organizing meetings, conferences and congresses in the area. Lately, the Bucovina tourist area has grown in popularity, but it is not exploited as it should. It is therefore necessary to take action in this regard, by promoting authentic Bucovina values. Tourist branding consists of identifying and creating, then exploiting sustainable competitive advantages, in this case being the strengths of the Bucovina product or tourist area.

We have to deal with the development of a tourism product (from the point of view of marketing), its launch on the tourism market and especially the connection between the consumer and the product on account of the qualities of the product (or its "uniqueness").

Branding (ie brand policy) has been an activity for centuries to differentiate the products of a producer from others.

Although the use of trademarks has been attested for 6000 years ago, both in the Mediterranean and the Middle East peoples, the phenomenon has developed a lot in recent centuries. Although European craft cooperatives were forced to apply so-called corporate brands since medieval times, brand names appeared only at the beginning of the sixteenth century, in the form of the name of the manufacturer that was printed on whiskey barrels, serving not only to identify products , but also to prevent the replacement of cheaper products by tavern owners.

The concept evolved and, in the 18th century, tobacco and perfume industries, the name of the manufacturer was replaced by names and pictures of animals, places of origin or names of famous people. The aim was to strengthen the brand-product associations so that consumers can more easily remember the product and differentiate it from those of competition.

The modern age in the history of the brand begins in the nineteenth century (Eminescu, 1974; Farquhar, 1990), when the brand began to be used to add value to the product with the help of associations. It is the moment of the emergence of brands that resist today: Henkel, Coca-Cola, Kodak, Lever, Mercedes etc.

As we can see, if in the antiquity the role of the mark was purely administrative, with the passage of time, the mark was increasingly used to signal and guarantee a certain level of quality and, in the last two centuries, to add value utilitarian and symbolic of the marked product, with the help of marketing communication in general and advertising in particular.

The word "brand" derives from the word "brand" in Old Norse, which means 'burn or mark', being the term used by cattle owners when it comes to marking animals to identify them.

Although the origin of the word is well-known, the definitions are numerous and often difficult to compare, since they differ even as scope. This is partly due to the different perspectives (of the consumer or the manufacturer) or philosophy (the plus-product approach or the holistic approach) from which they go.

In addition, the definition of the marks varies according to their purpose and characteristics or the domain to which they are compared. Here are some of the most important approaches to branding. The American Marketing Association adopts a manufacturer-oriented definition when claiming that a trademark is: a name, term, sign, symbol or design, or a combination thereof designed to help identify the goods and services of a seller or group of vendors; and to distinguish them from those of competition '.

However, the key to branding, according to this definition, is the choice of a name, logo, symbol, packaging or other attribute that helps identify a product and differentiate it from others. These different components of the brand, which identify and differentiate it, are called brand elements.

In fact, in creating a marketer, they have a lot of options in choosing the brand elements to help identify the product. They must be appealing and consistent with the consumer's perceptions of the product. Criticized for its product orientation, the definition focuses on differentiation based on visual features (brand elements).

OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this study is to identify the Bucovina tourist area as a renowned national and international brand. As for the tourist brand, it is the image element that identifies the tourism products or services of a tourist area or regions that generate the specificity of the area.

Each tourist area is distinguished by certain elements, for example, the Bucovina area has a specific folk harbor, traditional Bucovina cuisine, hospitality of the area's inhabitants, specific crafts.

METHODOLOGY

In order to carry out the present study, the specialized bibliography, referring to the brand and branding of the area, of the city of Suceava, was consulted (Anholt 2006, Benoit 2002, Kotler 2002, Kotler 2006, Kotler 2009, Kotler 2010, Rotar 2000, Popescu 2007, , 2010). Suceava County City Hall elaborated and a promotion strategy specific to the Bucovina area.

An area with an efficient brand highlights elements such as nature, landscapes, good weather, relaxing ambience, accessibility, infrastructure (all these form the artistic image), but also historical vestiges, art monuments, regional culture (customs and traditions, etc.), tourist accommodation structures (hotels, motels, restaurants, bars, etc.), regional gastronomy (all of which form the psychological image), stimulate the regional economy (through its own products and services offered and consumed) and can contribute to sustainable development of the whole region. Marta Plumed in the article "Place branding process: Analysis of the

population as consumers of destination image" states that in marketing and branding strategies, given the perceptions of the inhabitants, it is essential that promotional actions convey an image that represents adequately place and its inhabitants.

This research considers that a destination brand can not be successful without taking into account the perspective of residents. Thanks to a quantitative study of the Zaragoza case (Spain), a research model is presented to analyze the attitude and perception of brand usefulness and the perceived image.

The results confirm that the attitude of the inhabitants is the main variable to get a good image of the destination through a branding strategy, which will depend on the brand's usefulness.

Brand identity and brand image are the ingredients for a successful brand of destination (A.F.Stâncioiu,).

III. The main destination brand models in tourism studies

A trademark is a trademark that refers to a defined geographic region, understood by tourists as a single entity, with a political and legislative framework for tourism marketing (Buhalis, 2000). Destinations are an amalgam of travel products, offering experience for consumers. This amalgam of tourist products and services offered by a destination is consumed by tourists as a destination during the stay. This amalgam of tourist products and services offered by a destination is consumed by tourists as a destination during the stay. Instead, Cai (2002) defines destination branding as "selecting a mix of consistent elements to identify and distinguish the brand by building the positive image." Further on, he explains that the main purpose of creating value for destination is building a brand image to identify the most relevant associations and strengthening their links with the brand. In other studies, Kaplanidou and Vogt (2003) define the destination mark on "how consumers perceive their destination in their minds."

It is about capturing the distinctive features of branding and communicating these elements through brand components.

Kaplanidou and Vogt identify and designate a branding model to create and manage the value of the location from a tourist perspective. Includes many components that work together to form the destination brand.

In the first case, Cai's model (2002) considers the branding of the destination as a recursive process that revolves around the central axis, consisting of a mix of brand elements, brand identity - the model core - and brand image building.

The process described in the model begins with the careful selection of one or more brand elements. The purpose of the model is to define and build brand identity.

In the Kaplanidou and Vogt (2003) model, brand identity is based on a set of unique brand associations: these associations involve a promise to customers. Instead, in the second case, Hankinson's (2004) - the "relational network of the brand" - is a brand and four categories of brand relationships. These relationships are dynamic and develop over time. Stakeholders' partners can also change as the mark develops and repositions. The purpose of the mark is the identity of a place, the development plan and communication with the local brand.

It can be the vision of one or more organizations and could be defined by three elements (Hankinson, 2004):

- Performance of the brand. This is characterized by functional attributes, symbolic attributes and experimental attributes;

- Brand positioning. It defines the brand's benchmark in terms of competitiveness by identifying attributes.

- The reality of the brand. The development of the basic brand does not aim to create an image that presents an extremely important image, brand identity is a means of selling the place, as some authors suggest (Barke, Harrop, 1994).

IV A proposal of Destination Branding Model

In the case of destination - as illustrated in the previous section - the analysis of resources, skills and site capabilities is the basis for defining the identity of the destination brand. In branding the destination brand proposal proposal, brand identity is based on six elements:

- Mark culture refers to the system of features based on the cultural aspects of the people (customs and traditions, cultural events, gastronomy, etc.) and anthropic objectives (historical sites, monuments, archaeological sites, churches, etc.). Often this is the essence of a destination and this is its proposal of fundamental value;

- The character of the mark is related to the internal constitution, the way it is perceived in terms of integrity, trust and honesty (Upshaw, 1995).

-The brand personality is the set of human characteristics that are associated with the destination. This includes more features such as sincerity, enthusiasm or competence (Aaker J., 1997) or gender, age, socio-economic class, and human personality traits such as warmth and sentimentality (Aaker, 1996);
Brand names are often the initial destination name, in native language or English: this choice is more important because it is closely linked to the target tourism communication strategy;
-Logos trademarks (and symbols) are a fundamental element for defining the brand of a destination. A beautiful view, a famous monument or a unique tradition are examples of symbols;
-Sign-branding is based on the main functional, emotional or experimental attributes of the destination, related to the benefits and value offered by the site offer.

Brand Communication & Positioning Strategy

This way we can identify a brand of the Bucovina tourism product.

Brand Character - the Bucovina area is a historic destination and tourists are attracted by the churches and monasteries, which are renowned for its interior and exterior paintings; this area is of particular tourist interest and variety of landscapes;

Brand Culture-Habits and traditions, cultural events, gastronomy: painting of icons, eggs; Christmas traditions, Easter, painting exhibitions;

Brand Personality-hospitable, welcoming, true Bucovina people;

Brand Symbols-

Brand Name-Bucovina - an international destination;

Brand Slogan-„Hai in Bucovina,,

V.Swot analysis of Bucovina area

The strong points of the Bucovina tourist product:

- alternative tourism potential, traditional houses, handicraft, high natural potential, special relief, well preserved natural environment, attractive natural landscapes, local gastronomic specialties, traditional cuisine, New Year's customs, masks, traditional music and dances, .
- tourist resorts: Vatra Dornei (balneo-climatic) Câmpulung Moldovenesc, mineral springs, folklore and festivals, historical and ethnographic museums, medieval fortresses, ceramic exhibitions and traditional painting, the possibility of organizing a touristic circuit (the tour of the monasteries being the most requested) crafting black ceramics (Margeia).
- the local population is welcoming and open to tourism, and local authorities have identified tourism as an activity that could lead to the economic development of the region.
- tourist infrastructure in certain areas can be developed from scratch.
- the multitude of forms of relief practiced in Bucovina, itinerant tourism with cultural valences, spa tourism, rural tourism, transit tourism etc.

Weaknesses

- the mentality of people to make money quickly, people's indifference to the environment
- insufficient training of specialists in the tourism industry, lack of motivation of the staff
- low interest in investment
- disturbance of transport due to access routes
- the apparent poverty seen from the outside and the impression of neglecting monuments right in the historical areas.
- insufficient promotion of tourist objectives

Opportunities

- developing new tourist resorts - Câmpulung, Cacica, Botus,
- Fellowship of a Tourism Scholarship in Suceava
- the organization of rental of traditional houses
- provision of reception facilities with conference rooms, seminars
- establishing a network of tourist information centers near the main tourist attractions
- Encourage the development of new forms of tourism (Scientific Adventure)
- Improving infrastructure by implementing projects funded by European funds.
- increased interest of tourists from the Republic of Moldova and Ukraine for the mountain area

Threats

- the carelessness of the authorities towards the degradation of some monuments of art and architecture
- the development of the Maramures tourism product
- falling real population incomes, inflation
- The instability of government policies on tourism and taxation
- dimension of spare time availability
- Increasing competitiveness between regions and lack of collaboration between them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the SWOT analysis, due to the variety of natural and anthropic tourism potential, as well as the customs and traditions specific to the Bucovina area, of the tourist resorts in the area, for this area can be identified a brand specific to the Bucovina tourist area.

This brand can be given a name, a symbol, to get a renowned image through effective promotion both nationally and internationally in order to attract as many tourists as possible.

CONCLUSION

Through adequate support, the Bucovina area will become a renowned brand of national and international interest. Due to its varied tourist potential and suitable tourist facilities, Bucovina will attract tourists from all corners of the world. This area is also distinguished by the customs and traditions of Christmas, the New Year's Eve, Easter, as well as by the gastronomic specialties, which appeal to the tourists from the country and abroad. Mountain resorts such as Vatra Dornei, Câmpulung, mineral springs, medieval fortresses (Suceava), ceramic exhibitions and painting give the possibility of organizing a tourist circuit in the area.

REFERENCES

- [1] AAKER, D. (1991), *Managing Brand Equity. Capitalizing on the Value of a brand names*, The FreePress, New York.
- [2] AAKER, D. (1996), "Measuring brand equity across products and markets", *California Management Review*, n°3, spring, pp. 102-120.
- [3] AAKER, D. JOACHIMSTHALER, E. (2000) *Brand Leadership: The Next Level of Brand Revolution*, Hardcover, New York.
- [4] Anholt –Place branding and public diplomacy, October 2006, vol.2 issue pp.271-272;
- [5] Bouaru C.- Tourism Development Strategies in Bucovina,, Jurnal of tourism, Nr.2,2006
- [6] 6.BUHALIS, D. (2000),"Marketing the competitive destination of the future", *Tourism Management*, Vol. 21, pp. 97-116
- [7] Cătoiu I.,Balaure V.,- Tourism marketing, Ed.Uranus, București,2005
- [8] Delia Andreea Fratu- The marketing mix of the tourist destination, Application for the Braşov area, Brasov ,2012
- [9] Gavra(Juravle) A.I., Sasu C., TerecL.Vlad- The destination image of Bucovina among Romanian tourists, articol publicat la Revista Cross-Cultural Management.
- [10] Ispas, A., -Tourism marketing, Braşov, Ed.Universităţii ,2011
- [11] Ionescu, G., Murariu, A., - Sustainable development of Romanian tourism by designing competitive tourism products,2005
- [12] Kotler P.-Marketing, Management, Pearson Prentice Hall 2002 ,2009
- [13] Kotler P.-Principles of Marketing ,Pearson Prentice Hall, 2006
- [14] Kotler P.-Marketing for hospitality and tourism, Pearson Prentice Hall, 2010
- [15] Nedelea Al., Nedelea Oana- Interdisciplinary studies, Ed.Did.şiPed., Bucureşti,2013.
- [16] Al. Nedelea, , Tourism Marketing Policies, Ed. Economică, Bucureşti, 2003, p. 216
- [17] Lovelock C., Wirtz J.-Services Marketing-People, Technology, Strategy, USA,2007).
- [18] Rotaru I, Developing the tourist destination - course notes, Ed. Alma Mater,Sibiu, 2009.
- [19] Stăncioiu A.F.- Marketing planning in tourism, Editura Economică, Bucureşti, 2005
- [20] Stăncioiu A.F.- Picture of the tourist destination - elements of support in the construction of the regional tourist brand, article published in Theoretical and Applied Magazine vol.XVIII(2011), No.2(555)pp.139-152
- [21] Snak, O.,- Tourism Economy, Ed.Expert, Bucureşti,2006
- [22] Snak O.- Marketing in the Tourism Industry, Management and Tourism Institute, Bucureşti,1999
- [23] Tourism Development and Promotion Strategy in Suceava County, Prefect Institution, Suceava County.

Web Resources:

- [1] http://www.prefecturasuceava.ro/prog_dezv/2010/Actiuni_2010.pdf
- [2] <http://mdrt.ro/turism/promovare-turistica>
- [3] <http://www.romanianmonasteries.org/ro/bucovina>
- [4] <http://www.bucovinaturism.ro>